

Calibrating POI-based Synthetic Speech Detection

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Abstract

Recent advances in deep learning have yielded increasingly sophisticated speech generation systems (Text-To-Speech or Voice Conversion algorithms) capable of producing realistic synthetic speech material that is often indistinguishable from human voices. Although these technologies support a wide range of legitimate applications, they also facilitate malicious uses, including impersonation and misinformation, thereby posing significant societal threats. As a result, synthetic speech detection has emerged as an urgent research focus. Despite numerous proposed methods, a persistent generalization problem remains: detectors struggle to classify out-of-domain samples unseen during training, hence adapting and staying consistent when facing real-world scenarios.

We tackle this limitation with a Person-of-Interest framework that exploits speaker-specific characteristics for Synthetic Speech Detection, thereby enhancing generalizability across diverse generators. Specifically, we introduce an ensemble approach that addresses a previously unstudied calibration problem: the system uses only recording-level statistics to self-calibrate, leveraging the abstraction capabilities of a large-scale, pre-trained audio model. Experiments demonstrate that our method achieves strong performance, high generalizability, and robustness across various datasets.

CCS Concepts

• **Security and privacy** → *Privacy protections*; **Authentication**; **Spoofing attacks**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Ensemble methods**; *Artificial intelligence*.

Keywords

Audio Forensics, Synthetic Speech Detection, Large Audio Models, Person of Interest protection

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1 Introduction

The rapid advancement in synthetic speech technologies (notably Text-To-Speech or Voice Conversion systems) now enables effortless creation of high-quality artificial voices, offering benefits like voice restoration for impaired individuals [14], but also enabling

malicious uses such as deepfake fraud and/or misinformation. This double-edged sword presents ethical and security challenges. Although analysts [22, 29] argue that 2024 “wasn’t quite the year of AI elections”, documented cases, such as the fabricated imitation of Joe Biden disseminating false voting instructions [30], demonstrate the technology’s potential for misuse.

As mentioned in [8] but also recognized by mainstream media [21], synthetic speech is hard to detect, and the proliferation of such threats emphasizes the critical importance of robust synthetic speech detection systems, capable of distinguishing genuine human speech from potentially malicious machine-generated audio. These threats might not only become more frequent in the future, but could also evolve into language-agnostic tools, posing a growing global risk and challenge.

Current synthetic speech detections (SSD) systems predominantly employ supervised learning approaches, leveraging acoustic and/or spectral features extracted from audio signals. RawNet2 [27], for example, feeds the raw waveform to an end-to-end model in which the first layers act as learnable filterbanks, allowing the model to learn the most relevant features for the task. SFAT-Net-3 [7] relies on an explainable multi-task transformer for speech formant analysis, and uses bottleneck features to drive a synthesis detection branch. Some of these methods have the advantage of being explainable, even if they struggle to generalize to novel or evolving spoofing techniques not encountered during training [18].

Other more recent systems rely on the extraction of embeddings from large-scale pre-trained models like XLS-R, Hubert or Whisper [2, 25]. These embeddings then act as inputs to a deep learning method [32]. For example, [33] found that using various hidden layers of XLS-R [2] (based on wav2vec2.0 [3]) as input to a classification model could yield promising results. These methods, however, suffer from limited explainability, as they rely on pre-trained models that function as opaque black boxes - trained on diverse datasets for multiple tasks without transparent decision-making processes.

These issues highlight the need for adaptable, scalable solutions that can keep pace with the sophistication of synthetic speech generators.

Another method for synthetic content detection, the Person of Interest (POI) approach, was introduced in [1] as a visual analysis of deepfakes attacks targeting influential political figures. It was later adapted to SSD, notably by [23, 24], and consists of shifting the SSD approach to another one: Person of Interest for SSD (POI). Instead of trying to answer the question: “Was this sentence uttered by a human being?”, the question becomes “was this sentence uttered by *this* human being?”.

To tackle this problem, [24] leveraged a large-scale pre-trained model to develop a solution that is fully training-free. This method is based on the comparison of cosine similarity measurements to a fixed threshold that authenticates, or not, the file. It requires a

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reference set of real speech segments belonging to the person of interest, as well as the suspected file that needs to be authenticated.

In this work, we further investigate the potential of the POI approach for SSD by improving on the existing methodology. We apply a new auto-calibration methodology that allows the system to generalize to out-of-distribution data and to real world cases, while keeping the principles and requirements established by the original work: leveraging the capabilities of large-scale pre-trained audio models to develop a solution that is fully training and calibration free, and that doesn't require a large amount of speech examples to give results.

To this end, we use four statistical and machine-learning based auto-calibrating approaches. To improve the accuracy, robustness and generalizability, we find optimal weights and create an ensemble framework that is capable of auto-calibrating itself, thus eliminating the need to manually set a threshold. This Zero-Shot approach bypasses the need for speech generating method knowledge, and obtain consistent results over several different datasets.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the original methodology and the issues encountered. Section 3 outlines our proposal and details the choices made, the results of which are presented in Section 4, along with the corresponding data processing steps. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of our findings and directions for future research.

2 Training-free synthetic speech detection via Person-of-Interest analysis

2.1 Person-of-interest paradigm

In the following, we adopt the person-of-interest (POI) paradigm proposed by Pianese et al. in [24], where *i*) the identity of the speaker in a file under analysis is known, and *ii*) a reference set $\mathcal{R} = \{r_i\}$ containing natural audio segments for that speaker is available.

The intuition behind the POI-paradigm is that rather than replying to the question “Is this voice synthetic?”, synthesis detection algorithms should address the question “Does this voice belong to the alleged speaker?”, thus reframing the issue into a matter of speaker verification.

Therefore, to perform synthesis detection, the audio under test x and the reference set \mathcal{R} are compared in an embedding space generated by a large pre-trained audio model as outlined in Figure 1.

Let us denote with ω_{r_i} and ω_x the embeddings of the i -th reference file and of x , respectively. According to the POI algorithm, synthesis detection should be performed on the basis of a simple similarity thresholding:

$$x = \begin{cases} \text{synthetic } (H_1) & \text{if } \max_{r_i \in \mathcal{R}} \cos(x, r_i) < \tau^* \\ \text{natural } (H_0) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with

$$\cos(A, B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\|_2 \|B\|_2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}}. \quad (2)$$

denoting the cosine similarity.

In their work, Pianese et Al. [24] found that BEATs [6] was the best embedding extractor among those tested.

BEATs is a self-supervised learning framework designed to learn high-quality audio representations consisting of a jointly trained acoustic tokenizer and audio self-supervised learning model, that mutually improved each other on various tasks through several iterations. The result is a semantically rich embedding space that is robust to disturbances and performs well in various audio and speech classification tasks.

The optimal decision threshold τ^* in eq. (1) was selected empirically on the InTheWild dataset (the details of which will be provided in Section 4) across several alternative sizes of the reference set, and was finally set equal to 0.857.

2.2 Calibration of the decision threshold

Even though the POI-based methods in [24] are inherently generalizable due to the use of natural reference recordings for the comparison, the use of a fixed detection threshold $\tau^* = 0.857$ does not appear to be a reasonable choice.

A fixed decision threshold in a machine learning models is often limiting to its generalizability, since it assumes that optimal classification boundaries remain constant across different datasets or operating conditions. In practice, however, factors such as class imbalance, distribution shifts, or varying noise levels can alter the relationship between model confidence scores and true class membership, making a single threshold suboptimal. In turn, the shift in the decision boundary may lead to degraded performance when the model is deployed in real-world scenarios, the variability of which renders a fixed threshold unsuitable.

To verify our concerns, we evaluated the POI-based method in [24] on both the InTheWild dataset [18] for which the threshold τ^* was originally selected, and on the ubiquitous ASvspoof2019 LA Eval subset [31], obtaining the ROC curves shown in Figure 2

On these ROC-AUC curves, we highlighted both the Equal Error Rate (EER) threshold and the operating point associated with the manual threshold $\tau^* = 0.857$. While the EER is very close to

Figure 1: Methodology proposed by [24]. Audio signals are fed to a large-scale pre-trained model to extract their embeddings. After a pooling operation, cosine similarities are calculated between the test embeddings ω_x and the various reference embeddings ω_{r_i} , $\forall r_i \in \mathcal{R}$. A decision is then made based on statistical analysis.

Table 1: Comparison of the results obtained using Accuracy & F1-score metrics. EER corresponds to the results obtained using the EER threshold, Manual Threshold corresponds to the results obtained using the 0.857 threshold (as mentioned in [24]). For each value, we report a Δ corresponding to its difference with the EER.

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold		$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold	
	Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)		Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)
3	92.2	92.0	88.0 (-4.2)	86.6 (-5.4)	3	82.7	83.5	63.4 (-19.3)	73.1 (-10.4)
5	94.3	94.2	92.0 (-2.3)	91.5 (-2.7)	5	83.8	84.6	61.7 (-22.1)	72.3 (-12.3)
10	95.1	95.1	94.8 (-0.3)	94.7 (-0.4)	10	84.8	85.5	60.1 (-24.7)	71.4 (-14.1)
20	96.1	96.1	96.0 (-0.1)	96.0 (-0.1)	20	85.8	86.7	58.2 (-27.6)	70.5 (-16.2)
50	97.1	97.1	96.5 (-0.6)	96.5 (-0.6)	50	85.9	86.7	55.8 (-30.1)	69.3 (-17.4)

(a) InTheWild [18]

(b) ASVspoof2019 LA Eval [31]

the operating point on the InTheWild dataset, the performance degrades severely on the ASVspoof2019 LA Eval subset, in which the expected False Positive Rate (FPR) would be around 80%.

Table 1 reports in detail the full outcome of the experiments: The proposed fixed threshold τ^* is well suited for the InTheWild dataset, where the performance loss compared to the EER operating point is negligible and mostly lower than 3% for both precision and recall. In the results obtained on the ASVspoof2019 dataset, however, we observe a large discrepancy in the results: The performance degrades severely and even approach randomness when the number of reference files is high—a consequence of the sharp increase of the false positive rate that we could observe in Figure 2.

This experiment confirms our concerns that, while the original POI-based methodology allows the system to efficiently leverage large pre-trained models to perform synthesis detection, the calibration of its decision threshold, and therefore the effective generalizability of the approach, remains an unsolved issue.

Therefore, in the following section, we propose an automatic calibration mechanism based on the sole statistics of the natural reference recordings - that are expected to be much more stable than those of synthetically generated content - with the potential to overcome the shortcomings of the original proposal.

3 Proposed Auto-Calibration Framework

Our proposed auto-calibration framework relies on four distinct calibration approaches, that we developed independently and then combined in a final ensemble method.

The common denominator between the approaches, is that they strive to determine a reasonable heuristic that, given a test file x and a set of reference files \mathcal{R} , can infer whether x belongs to the same distribution based solely on the statistics of the reference set.

Each calibration mechanism will be described in the following, first in isolation, and then in combination with other alternatives.

3.1 Comparison with the closest file in the reference set ('Closest')

This first calibration method is based on the analysis of the reference file $r^* \in \mathcal{R}$ that is the closest to x .

Figure 2: ROC-AUC curves for InTheWild (top) & ASVspoof2019 LA Eval (bottom) - $|\mathcal{R}| = \{5, 20\}$. Are highlighted 2 operating points : the EER threshold and the Manual Threshold obtained with the 0.857 threshold [14]

Let us denote with $\text{sim}(x, r_i)$ the cosine similarity between x and a reference file in \mathcal{R} in the embedding space, i.e.,

$$\text{sim}(x, r_i) = \frac{\omega_x \cdot \omega_{r_i}}{\|\omega_x\| \|\omega_{r_i}\|}, \quad (3)$$

with $\|\cdot\|$ denoting the l2 norm. The closest reference file r^* can be determined by imposing

$$r^* = \arg \max_{r_i \in \mathcal{R}} \text{sim}(x, r_i), \quad (4)$$

i.e., by picking the reference file that has the highest similarity to the one under analysis.

To determine if x might be part of the distribution, we use r^* as prototype to compute the similarities that would occur between a natural recording and the other reference files. Therefore, we first

compute a prototype set of similarities

$$\mathcal{S}^* = \{\text{sim}(r^*, r_i)\} \quad \forall r_i \in \mathcal{R} \setminus r^* \quad (5)$$

and then compare it with the similarity between x and r^* :

- $\text{sim}(x, r^*) \leq \text{mean}_{0.05}(\mathcal{S}^*) \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $\text{sim}(x, r^*) > \text{mean}_{0.05}(\mathcal{S}^*) \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

where $\text{mean}_{0.05}$ denotes the truncated mean value, i.e., the mean obtained after removing 5% of the extreme values in the input set.

3.2 Comparison with the center of mass of the reference set ('COM')

Rather than relying on a single reference file as prototype, this second calibration method uses as a prototype the center-of-mass of the entire reference distribution.

Let us denote with $\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}$ the center of mass of \mathcal{R} , i.e.,

$$\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{R}|} \sum_{r_i \in \mathcal{R}} \omega_{r_i}. \quad (6)$$

A corresponding prototype set of similarities can be obtained as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{COM}} = \left\{ \frac{\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} \cdot \omega_{r_i}}{\|\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}\| \|\omega_{r_i}\|} \right\} \quad \forall r_i \in \mathcal{R}, \quad (7)$$

where again $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the l2 norm.

To determine if x might be part of the distribution, we compare the prototype set with the similarity between x and the center-of-mass:

- $\frac{\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} \cdot \omega_x}{\|\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}\| \|\omega_x\|} \leq \min(\mathcal{S}_{\text{COM}}) \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $\frac{\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} \cdot \omega_x}{\|\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}\| \|\omega_x\|} > \min(\mathcal{S}_{\text{COM}}) \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

For small reference sets ($|\mathcal{R}| \leq 10$) using the minimum directly might be very penalizing. Therefore, in those cases, we found it useful to relax the constraint and use a value slightly lower than the absolute minimum, and impose:

- $\frac{\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} \cdot \omega_x}{\|\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}\| \|\omega_x\|} \leq 0.95 \min(\mathcal{S}_{\text{COM}}) \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $\frac{\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}} \cdot \omega_x}{\|\bar{\omega}_{\mathcal{R}}\| \|\omega_x\|} > 0.95 \min(\mathcal{S}_{\text{COM}}) \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

3.3 Outlier detection by means of the Isolation Forest ('IF') analysis

Isolation Forest [15] is an unsupervised anomaly detection algorithm that constructs binary trees to isolate data points.

Figure 3 presents a visual explanation of the principles behind the

Figure 3: A visual explanation of the Isolation Forest. It requires fewer splits to isolate an anomalous point.

Figure 4: A visual example of the Local Outlier Factor output. Outliers are the points that have the highest outlier scores.

approach: Isolation Forest associates each data point with the number of splits required to separate it from all other elements of the dataset, following a recursive binary partitioning. The partitioning is repeated on several subsets of the data, using random dimensions in the input data to build a forest of casual trees. Points that can be isolated with a low number of splits across different configurations are marked as anomalies.

To apply Isolation Forest, we propose to merge the entire set of references \mathcal{R} with the file x under investigation, and to let the algorithm create an anomaly set \mathcal{A}_{IF} , instructing it to mark 10% of the references as possible outliers. The synthesis detection heuristic is then straightforward:

- $x \in \mathcal{A}_{\text{IF}} \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $x \notin \mathcal{A}_{\text{IF}} \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

3.4 Outlier detection by means of Local Outlier Factor ('LOF') analysis

Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [4] is an unsupervised anomaly detection algorithm that relies on local densities to detect spurious data.

Figure 4 presents a visualization of the output produced by the algorithm. Each data point is assigned a score computed by comparing the local density of the point itself – in essence, the number of points within a predefined distance – with the local density of all its neighbors. Points within dense regions that are nevertheless isolated from their neighbors can be labeled as anomalies.

To apply local outlier factor analysis, we once again merge the entire set of references \mathcal{R} with the file x under investigation, and let the algorithm create an anomaly set \mathcal{A}_{LOF} , instructing it to mark 20% of the references as possible outliers. The synthesis detection algorithm depends entirely on the anomaly detection outcome:

- $x \in \mathcal{A}_{\text{LOF}} \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $x \notin \mathcal{A}_{\text{LOF}} \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

Table 2: F1-scores (expressed in %) for the different approaches on InTheWild & ASVspoof2019 LA Eval after calibrating on ASVspoof2019 LA Dev. EER corresponds to F1 score obtained using the EER threshold, Manual Threshold corresponds to the F1 score obtained using the fixed 0.857 threshold (as mentioned in [24]). We also report the F1-score for the 4 auto-calibrated approaches. For each value, we report a Δ corresponding to its difference with the EER.

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER	Manual Threshold (Δ)	COM (Δ)	Closest (Δ)	IF (Δ)	LOF (Δ)
3	92.0	86.6 (-5.4)	85.5 (-6.5)	87.3 (-4.7)	79.2 (-12.8)	82.3 (-9.7)
5	94.2	91.5 (-2.7)	92.4 (-1.8)	91.5 (-2.7)	83.0 (-11.2)	85.8 (-8.4)
10	95.1	94.7 (-0.4)	87.5 (-7.6)	93.7 (-1.4)	83.8 (-11.3)	88.0 (-7.1)
20	96.1	96.0 (-0.1)	90.8 (-5.3)	94.6 (-1.5)	88.7 (-7.4)	88.8 (-7.3)
50	97.1	96.5 (-0.6)	91.6 (-5.5)	94.1 (-3.0)	90.2 (-6.9)	88.9 (-8.2)

(a) InTheWild [18]

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER	Manual Threshold (Δ)	COM (Δ)	Closest (Δ)	IF (Δ)	LOF (Δ)
3	83.5	73.1 (-10.4)	79.6 (-3.9)	79.5 (-4.0)	71.2 (-12.3)	72.3 (-11.2)
5	84.6	72.3 (-12.3)	79.7 (-4.9)	81.0 (-3.6)	73.2 (-11.4)	77.1 (-7.5)
10	85.5	71.4 (-14.1)	81.6 (-3.9)	82.0 (-3.5)	72.9 (-12.6)	81.9 (-3.6)
20	86.7	70.5 (-16.2)	83.2 (-3.5)	81.3 (-5.4)	78.5 (-8.2)	83.2 (-3.5)
50	86.7	69.3 (-17.4)	82.3 (-4.4)	77.1 (-9.6)	81.0 (-5.7)	83.1 (-3.6)

(b) ASVspoof 2019 Eval [31]

3.5 Auto-calibration Ensemble

Each calibration method presented so far has its own positive aspects: The *Closest* method (Section 3.1) is well suited for sparse embeddings, and relies on a class prototype from the very same reference set to anchor its decision mechanism; The *COM* method (Section 3.2) is well suited for dense clusters, in which the center-of-mass can reliably be used as a good descriptor for the entire population; The *IF* method (Section 3.3) takes advantage of sub-sampling to efficiently partition datasets, which helps the analysis of large reference sets; The *LOF* method (Section 3.4) is able to handle populations distributed with locally different densities - e.g., what might happen using reference files of different qualities.

To verify the overall usefulness of the four methods, we run a preliminary experiment to compare the F1 scores obtained using the corresponding decision mechanisms on the eval partition of the ASVspoof2019 LA and InTheWild datasets. The results of the experiments, reported in Table 2, are very promising.

In general, the performance of each calibration method depends on the number of reference files: Similarity-based approaches (*Closest* and *COM*) seem to perform well for smaller reference sets, while outlier detection algorithms (*IF* and *LOF*) are better suited for larger ones. More importantly, the performance loss compared to the EER operating point (indicated as a Δ in Table 2) does not show extreme deviations between the two dataset distributions. This is a striking difference compared to what happens by using a fixed, manually-set, threshold: While the F1 performances are excellent on the InTheWild dataset for which the threshold was picked, they drastically decrease on the ASVspoof2019 LA partition.

In light of the results above, we propose to combine the four different auto-calibration approaches into an ensemble model, using a decision fusion paradigm.

Let the outcome of each algorithm be denoted by o_{algo} , i.e.

$$o_{\text{algo}} \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \text{ is synthetic } (H_1) \text{ according to } \textit{algo} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The decision can be fused by means of a weighted average, in which each weight parameter $w_{\text{algo}}^{|\mathcal{R}|}$ is set according to the size of the reference datasets. Let the fused outcome be defined as

$$o_{\text{autocalib}} = w_{\text{Closest}}^{|\mathcal{R}|} o_{\text{Closest}} + w_{\text{COM}}^{|\mathcal{R}|} o_{\text{COM}} + w_{\text{IF}}^{|\mathcal{R}|} o_{\text{IF}} + w_{\text{LOF}}^{|\mathcal{R}|} o_{\text{LOF}}. \quad (9)$$

If we impose that the sum of all weights is equal to one, synthesis detection can be performed according to:

- $o_{\text{autocalib}} > 0.5 \Rightarrow$ the file x is synthetic (H_1)
- $o_{\text{autocalib}} \leq 0.5 \Rightarrow$ the file x is natural (H_0)

The computational complexity of the proposed framework is dominated by *LOF*, which scales as $O(n^2)$. The other components scale more efficiently: *IF* operates in $O(n \cdot \log(n))$, while *COM* and *Closest* operate in $O(n)$, where n corresponds to $|\mathcal{R}|$. While this could be prohibitive for a large n , the maximum reference set size considered here is $n = 50$, rendering the complexity negligible for inference in practice.

4 Experimental results

4.1 Datasets

The performance of the detection ensemble presented in Section 3 was evaluated on four datasets used in the synthetic speech detection community: InTheWild [18], ASVspoof2019 [31], Spoof-Celeb [13] and LlamaPartialSpoof [16].

The *InTheWild* dataset consists of real audio recordings of celebrities and politicians with their associated audio deepfakes collected on social networks and video streaming platforms. It was collected

with the purpose of challenging detection algorithms to also discriminate between synthetic and natural content that has undergone unknown postprocessing. *ASVspoof2019* is a dataset collected for the 2019 edition of the Automatic Verification Spoofing and Countermeasure challenge. It consists of logical and physical access attacks using text-to-speech and voice conversion systems. The performance evaluation in the following sections was entirely performed on its *eval* partition. The *SpoofCeleb* corpus is a dataset that was generated after training 23 different TTS systems on the VoxCeleb1 dataset [20], a dataset containing speech examples from over 1 000 celebrities, which were acquired on social media and therefore underwent unknown postprocessing. Lastly, *LlamaPartialSpoof* is a dataset devised to also contain partially manipulated files, in which only certain portions of a recording are altered. This dataset includes both diffusion-based generators and proprietary commercial generators. For the following experiments, we consider a subset that only consists of fully spoofed audio extracts.

As highlighted in [8, 10, 19, 26], synthetic speech detection approaches can be biased by factors unrelated to the speech content, such as uneven distribution of silent segments, or hidden biases in the recording conditions (background noise, loudness, microphone characteristics, etc...). To try to mitigate the impact of these artifacts, we pre-processed the entire content to reduce the variability of controllable elements, and tried to ensure that the embedding space’s generation is more focused on genuine spoofing cues rather than artifacts.

We therefore started by removing the trailing/ending and silent parts of the speech signal using a Voice Activity Detection tool [28]. We then normalized the audio files to a target level of -23dB LUFS to comply with the EBU R128 broadcast standards [9], ensuring a consistent loudness across all recordings. All files were converted to 16-bit PCM and a 16 kHz sample rate. Finally, to avoid outlier effects caused by low-quality content, we removed the files with a SNR below 6.0 dB, using a Source Separation model [11] to assist the process.

4.2 Ensemble weights configuration

The ensemble auto-calibration method was configured by optimizing the weights in eq. (9) according to the development set of *ASVspoof2019 LA*. The development set consists of a few natural recordings and synthetic examples generated by older synthesis algorithms (a few not even relying on deep-learning based solutions), and is disjoint from the four sets used for performance evaluation. The weight optimization process is designed to leverage the strengths of individual models while mitigating their weaknesses in order to yield a more accurate and reliable final prediction.

As seen in Table 2, there is a noticeable disparity in the efficiency of the different approaches depending on the size of the reference set. To balance these disparities and improve overall performance, we determine optimal weights that harmonize the contributions of each model in the ensemble. Once these weights are established, they are fixed for consistency in evaluation and real-world use (these weights are optimized for our embedding extractor, and fixing them ensures stability and consistency across all subsequent evaluations and real-world applications), while also maintaining a

Figure 5: Impact of the weighting strategy for the calibration process, in terms of Accuracy and F1 score on the ASVspoof 2019 development subset.

deliberate balance among the different algorithms in our ensemble method.

The optimization was carried out using an exhaustive grid search: All weights were constrained to vary between 0.0 and 0.5 with a step of 0.05, resulting in the configurations shown in Table 3.

We also compared this solution with a complete lack of training strategy, i.e., when all weights are uniformly set to 0.25, independently of the size of the reference set. The outcome of the comparison can be inspected in Figure 5: On average, the weighting strategy has a small impact on the results, albeit always positive. Both solutions are more competitive than each isolated calibration strategy in Table 2, and the loss compared to the EER comparison is always negligible. This is a striking difference from the strong oscillations we observed before introducing the ensemble, and proves its effectiveness in balancing the positive and negative aspects of the four calibration methods it is composed of.

4.3 Results

For each evaluation dataset, we prepared several test trials, composed of a reference set \mathcal{R} with natural speech extracts, and a single

Table 3: Detailed weights of individual approaches for the ensemble method depending on $|\mathcal{R}|$

$ \mathcal{R} $	COM	Closest	IF	LOF
3	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.1
5	0.1	0.45	0.4	0.05
10	0.05	0.5	0.05	0.4
20	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.1
50	0.05	0.45	0.45	0.05

Table 4: Comparison of our results using the Accuracy & F1-score metrics. EER corresponds to the results obtained using the EER threshold, Manual Threshold corresponds to the results obtained using the 0.857 threshold (as mentioned in [24]). For each value, we report a Δ corresponding to its difference with the EER.

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold		Our approach	
	Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)
3	82.7	83.5	63.4 (-19.3)	73.1 (-10.4)	81.1 (-1.6)	79.7 (-3.8)
5	83.8	84.6	61.7 (-22.1)	72.3 (-12.3)	81.0 (-2.8)	79.3 (-5.3)
10	84.8	85.5	60.1 (-24.7)	71.4 (-14.1)	83.1 (-1.7)	82.2 (-3.3)
20	85.8	86.7	58.2 (-27.6)	70.5 (-16.2)	84.0 (-1.8)	82.8 (-3.9)
50	85.9	86.7	55.8 (-30.1)	69.3 (-17.4)	84.2 (-1.7)	83.0 (-3.7)

(a) **ASVspoof 2019 Eval** [31]

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold		Our approach	
	Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)
3	92.2	92.0	88.0 (-4.2)	86.6 (-5.4)	83.0 (-9.2)	86.4 (-5.6)
5	94.3	94.2	92.0 (-2.3)	91.5 (-2.7)	91.5 (-2.8)	92.3 (-1.9)
10	95.1	95.1	94.8 (-0.3)	94.7 (-0.4)	92.7 (-2.4)	92.9 (-2.2)
20	96.1	96.1	96.0 (-0.1)	96.0 (-0.1)	93.8 (-2.3)	94.2 (-1.9)
50	97.1	97.1	96.5 (-0.6)	96.5 (-0.6)	92.9 (-4.2)	91.6 (-5.5)

(b) **InTheWild** [18]

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold		Our approach	
	Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)
3	82.8	82.9	73.0 (-9.8)	78.4 (-4.5)	82.7 (-0.1)	83.2 (0.3)
5	84.7	84.8	70.3 (-14.4)	76.9 (-7.9)	82.7 (-2.0)	81.1 (-3.7)
10	86.3	86.3	67.2 (-19.1)	75.2 (-11.1)	84.5 (-1.8)	83.4 (-2.9)
20	87.6	87.6	64.6 (-23.0)	73.8 (-13.8)	86.0 (-1.6)	84.7 (-2.9)
50	89.2	89.2	62.5 (-26.7)	72.7 (-16.5)	85.9 (-3.3)	84.8 (-4.4)

(c) **LlamaPartialSpoof** [16]

$ \mathcal{R} $	EER		Manual Threshold		Our approach	
	Acc.	F1	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)	Acc. (Δ)	F1 (Δ)
3	73.5	75.1	67.5 (-6.0)	58.2 (-16.9)	69.6 (-3.9)	68.1 (-7.0)
5	75.2	76.5	71.9 (-3.3)	67.5 (-9.0)	73.1 (-2.1)	72.0 (-4.5)
10	77.1	77.9	74.0 (-3.1)	68.5 (-9.4)	76.6 (-0.5)	76.1 (-1.8)
20	78.8	79.7	74.5 (-4.3)	67.8 (-11.9)	78.7 (-0.1)	80.1 (0.4)
50	81.1	81.7	73.7 (-7.4)	67.8 (-13.9)	78.5 (-2.6)	81.4 (-0.3)

(d) **SpoofCeleb** [13]

file x (either synthetic or natural) to be tested against it. We ensured congruency between the identity of the speaker in x and the one in the reference set \mathcal{R} , and balanced the trials to make sure that the number of synthetic and natural test files to be tested was identical across speakers. To avoid issues due to uneven result distribution, we repeated the experiments 10 times for each reference size $|\mathcal{R}| = 3, 5, 10, 20, 50$.

The evaluation results are reported in Table 4. For each dataset we compared the “theoretical best” results obtained at the EER operating point¹, with the results obtained using a fixed predefined threshold $\tau_{\text{fixed}} = 0.857$, and with the results obtained with our own approach.

We selected Accuracy and F1 as comparison metrics, since they provide complementary insights into performance. While accuracy measures the overall correctness of the predictions, F1 captures the balance between precision and recall, and therefore between false negatives and false positives.

The evaluation confirms that the use of a fixed predefined threshold is not advisable: While the performance using $\tau_{\text{fixed}} = 0.857$ on the InTheWild dataset is excellent, τ_{fixed} being very close to the optimal EER-based threshold, the performance drops dramatically for all other datasets under analysis. The most likely explanation for this behavior is that locking the detection threshold to a specific calibration distribution led to a complete lack of generalization, undermining the properties inherent to the POI-based approach.

On the other hand, our proposed approach relies solely on natural data for auto-calibrating itself. The performance is slightly worse than using $\tau_{\text{fixed}} = 0.857$ on the InTheWild dataset, but significantly better on all other datasets under analysis. Notably, the performance loss to the EER operating point is mostly less than 3%

of Accuracy and 5% of F1 (a very reasonable price to pay for ensuring generalization despite the lack of any previous knowledge of the evaluation data). Since we make sure that our class is balanced - i.e., the same number of input groups containing a tested audio file being natural or being synthetic - the slight asymmetry between the Accuracy metric and the F1 metric reveals the prevalence of either false negatives or false positives in the error types.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed an enhancement to the one-class detection strategy in [24], that leveraged prior knowledge of speaker identity by means of a comparison against a set of reference recordings.

Our proposal is an ensemble framework composed of four methods that auto-calibrate themselves to fit the input data. This framework is more robust and generalizable while preserving the original spirit of the original approach: a training-free framework powered by large-scale pre-trained audio models that offers a computationally efficient solution.

Whereas the baseline detection strategy relied on an optimal threshold determined post-hoc on a calibration set, and therefore still required some preliminary knowledge on the distribution of potential evaluation data, we proposed a generator-agnostic automatic calibration approach that only relies on natural reference data of the person-of-interest under analysis. While this comes at the cost of a slight performance loss, this zero-shot solution bypasses the need for preliminary knowledge, and generalizes well to various unseen synthetic speech generators.

On the negative side, this approach is limited in terms of result explainability, and relies entirely on the quality of the BEATs embeddings [6]. Previous research by [32] has shown that utilizing

¹Identified after evaluating the whole dataset as done in [24]

embeddings from semantically rich large-scale pre-trained models could improve the results even further, despite at the cost of a further loss of explainability.

In the future, we would thus like to test the sensitivity of the ensemble to different input embedding spaces for the POI-based synthetic speech detection backbone, such as HuBERT [12], WavLM [5], and XLS-R [2]. Furthermore, we would like to extend our approach by using embeddings derived from interpretable speech analysis or speaker verification networks [7, 17], potentially unlocking new spoofing detection ideas that could balance explainability, efficiency, adaptability, and generalizability.

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